

Supplementary Information

1. Supplementary Information 1

1.1. Survival data in vertebrates

In order to cover a wide range of realistic case study of wild vertebrates in our simulation framework we gathered demographic data from published CMR studies and database. Most of the survival data for mammals, birds, reptiles, and amphibians come from the Demographic Species Knowledge Index (Conde *et al.*, 2019) and were completed from literature in particular for fish and bat species (Lentini, Bird, Griffiths, Godinho, and Wintle, 2015). Complementary data used are summarised in Table S1.

There is a wide range of values of survival rates, from 0.2 to over 0.97, across both age classes and taxa considered. For short-lived species, juveniles and adults have both low survival rate (Fig. S1). However, for longer-lived species, there is an greater dispersion in the data with increased survival in adults associated with both high or low survival in juveniles. To limit our simulation scenarios, we chose 2 cases where juvenile survival was low when adult survival was low, which we considered as short-lived species and the opposite as long-lived species.

Figure1 – Relationship between adult and juvenile survival rates among 143 species.

species	genus	family	order	class	phylum	kingdom	source	varname	varvalue
Odocoileus hemionus	Odocoileus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.879
Odocoileus hemionus	Odocoileus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.823
Rangifer tarandus	Rangifer	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.844
Rangifer tarandus	Rangifer	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.94
Tragelaphus strepsiceros	Tragelaphus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.933
Tragelaphus strepsiceros	Tragelaphus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.889
Ovis canadensis	Ovis	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.946
Ovis canadensis	Ovis	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.911
Capreolus capreolus	Capreolus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.92
Capreolus capreolus	capreolus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.923
Ovis aries	Ovis	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.902
Alce alces	Alce	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.949
Cervus elaphus	Cervus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.955
Oreamnos americanus	Oreamnos	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.916
Equus ferus caballus	Equus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.975
Ovis dalli	Ovis	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.88
Bos taurus	Bos	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.902
Alce alces	Alce	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.976
Alce alces	Alce	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.952
Alce alces	Alce	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.976
Capra sp	Capra	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.929
Antilocapra americana	Antilocapra	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Adult_survival	0.978
Odocoileus hemionus	Odocoileus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.271
Odocoileus hemionus	Odocoileus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.334
Rangifer tarandus	Rangifer	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.489
Rangifer tarandus	Rangifer	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.567
Tragelaphus strepsiceros	Tragelaphus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.449
Tragelaphus strepsiceros	Tragelaphus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.446
Ovis canadensis	Ovis	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.564
Ovis canadensis	Ovis	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.355
Capreolus capreolus	Capreolus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.537
Capreolus capreolus	capreolus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.414
Ovis aries	Ovis	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.611
Alce alces	Alce	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.331
Cervus elaphus	Cervus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.615

species	genus	family	order	class	phylum	kingdom	source	varname	varvalue
Oreamnos americanus	Oreamnos	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.631
Equus ferus caballus	Equus	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.275
Ovis dalli	Ovis	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.773
Bos taurus	Bos	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.755
Alce alces	Alce	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.813
Alce alces	Alce	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.865
Alce alces	Alce	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.825
Capra sp	Capra	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.867
Antilocapra americana	Antilocapra	Cervidae	Artiodactyla	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[1]	Juvenile_survival	0.142
Common pipistrelle	Pipistrellus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[2]	Juvenile_survival	0.527
Common pipistrelle	Pipistrellus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[2]	Adult_survival	0.799
Nyctalus leisleri	Nyctalus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[3]	Adult_survival	0.91
Nyctalus leisleri	Nyctalus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[3]	Adult_survival	0.613
Halichoerus grypus	Nyctalus	Phocidae	Carnivora	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[4]	Adult_survival	0.89
Halichoerus grypus	Nyctalus	Phocidae	Carnivora	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[4]	Adult_survival	0.97
Carcharodon carcharias	Carcharodon	Lamnidae	Lamniformes	Chondrichthyesa	Chordata	Animalia	[5]	Juvenile_survival	0.632
Dipterus cf. intermedia	Dipterus	Rajidae	Rajiformes	Chondrichthyesa	Chordata	Animalia	[5]	Annual_survival	0.632
Rhincodon typus	Rhincodon	Rhincodontidae	Orectolobiformes	Chondrichthyesa	Chordata	Animalia	[6]	Juvenile_survival	0.59
Rhincodon typus	Rhincodon	Rhincodontidae	Orectolobiformes	Chondrichthyesa	Chordata	Animalia	[7]	Adult_survival	0.825
Fundulus heteroclitus	Fundulus	Fundulidae	Cyprinodontiformes	Actinopterygii	Chordata	Animalia	[8]	Annual_survival	0.87
Acipenser oxyrinchus oxyrinchus	Acipenser	Acipenseridae	Acipenseriformes	Actinopterygii	Chordata	Animalia	[9]	Annual_survival	0.88
Macroderma gigas	Macroderma	Megadermatidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[10]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.492
Macroderma gigas	Macroderma	Megadermatidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[10]	adultSurvival.avg	0.685
Myotis myotis	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[11]	adultSurvival.avg	0.719
Myotis myotis	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[11]	adultSurvival.avg	0.708
Chalinolobus morio	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[12]	adultSurvival.avg	0.72
Nyctophilus geoffroyi	Nyctophilus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[12]	adultSurvival.avg	0.42
Vespadelus vulturnus	Vespadelus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[12]	adultSurvival.avg	0.59
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[13]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.77
Myotis sodalis	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[14]	adultSurvival.avg	0.624
Corynorhinus townsendii	Corynorhinus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[15]	adultSurvival.avg	0.6
Corynorhinus townsendii	Corynorhinus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[15]	adultSurvival.avg	0.58
Corynorhinus townsendii	Corynorhinus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[15]	adultSurvival.avg	0.65
Corynorhinus townsendii	Corynorhinus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[15]	adultSurvival.avg	0.54
Corynorhinus townsendii	Corynorhinus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[15]	adultSurvival.avg	0.67

species	genus	family	order	class	phylum	kingdom	source	varname	varvalue
Corynorhinus townsendii	Corynorhinus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[15]	adultSurvival.avg	0.67
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	adultSurvival.avg	0.68
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.52
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	adultSurvival.avg	0.81
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.69
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	adultSurvival.avg	0.87
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.5
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	adultSurvival.avg	0.86
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.76
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	adultSurvival.avg	0.73
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[16]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.59
Myotis yumanensis	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[17]	adultSurvival.avg	0.84
Myotis yumanensis	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[17]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.74
Pipistrellus pipistrellus	Pipistrellus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[18]	adultSurvival.avg	0.56
Pipistrellus pipistrellus	Pipistrellus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[18]	adultSurvival.avg	0.75
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[19]	Survival	0.465
Myotis leibii	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[19]	Survival	0.697
Eptesicus fuscus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[19]	Survival	0.421
Myotis leibii	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[19]	Survival	0.757
Myotis lucifugus	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[20]	Survival	0.708
Myotis lucifugus	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[20]	Survival	0.816
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[21]	adultSurvival.avg	0.75
Myotis capaccinii	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[22]	adultSurvival.avg	0.943
Myotis capaccinii	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[22]	adultSurvival.avg	0.903
Eptesicus isabellinus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[23]	adultSurvival.avg	0.7
Eptesicus isabellinus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[23]	adultSurvival.avg	0.81
Eptesicus isabellinus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[23]	adultSurvival.avg	0.71
Eptesicus isabellinus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[23]	adultSurvival.avg	0.61
Eptesicus isabellinus	Eptesicus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[23]	adultSurvival.avg	0.58
Myotis bechsteinii	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[24]	adultSurvival.avg	0.79
Myotis daubentonii	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[24]	adultSurvival.avg	0.79
Nyctalus lasiopterus	Nyctalus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[24]	adultSurvival.avg	0.74
Nyctalus leisleri	Nyctalus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[24]	adultSurvival.avg	0.74
Plecotus auritus	Plecotus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[24]	adultSurvival.avg	0.79
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[25]	adultSurvival.avg	0.89

species	genus	family	order	class	phylum	kingdom	source	varname	varvalue
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[25]	adultSurvival.avg	0.55
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[25]	adultSurvival.avg	0.5
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[25]	adultSurvival.avg	0.91
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	adultSurvival.avg	0.77
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	adultSurvival.avg	0.65
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.54
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	adultSurvival.avg	0.79
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.71
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	adultSurvival.avg	0.58
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.47
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	adultSurvival.avg	0.75
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.71
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	adultSurvival.avg	0.67
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.57
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	adultSurvival.avg	0.81
Chalinolobus tuberculatus	Chalinolobus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[26]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.74
Myotis nattereri	Myotis	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[27]	Survival	0.86
Rhinolophus ferrumequinum	Rhinolophus	Rhinolophidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[28]	Survival	0.49
Rhinolophus ferrumequinum	Rhinolophus	Rhinolophidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[28]	Survival	0.91
Nyctalus leisleri	Nyctalus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[29]	juvenileSurvival.avg	0.45
Nyctalus leisleri	Nyctalus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[29]	adultSurvival.avg	0.76
Nyctalus leisleri	Nyctalus	Vespertilionidae	Chiroptera	Mammalia	Chordata	Animalia	[29]	adultSurvival.avg	0.69

Table1 – Complementary data to Conde et al. (2019) used to explore cross taxa survival rates (varvalue) in vertebrates, according to age class (varname).

2. Tag loss data in vertebrates

Species	Scientific Name	Class	Mark type	Sample size	Loss rate	Duration	Location	Conditions	Control	Source
Brown trout	<i>Salmo trutta</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	145	0.2-0.3	4 weeks	Peritoneal cavity	Laboratory	None	[30]
Bluegills	<i>Lepomis macrochirus</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	20	0-0.4	42 days	Dorsal musculature	Laboratory	None	[31]
Bluegills	<i>Lepomis macrochirus</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	20	0.1-0.2	42 days	Peritoneal cavity	Laboratory	None	[31]
Bluegills	<i>Lepomis macrochirus</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	20	0.4-1	42 days	Isthmus	Laboratory	None	[31]
Yellow perch	<i>Perca flavescens</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	20	0-0.5	42 days	Dorsal musculature	Laboratory	None	[31]
Yellow perch	<i>Perca flavescens</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	20	0-0.2	42 days	Peritoneal cavity	Laboratory	None	[31]
Yellow perch	<i>Perca flavescens</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	20	0.4-1	42 days	Isthmus	Laboratory	None	[31]
Muskellunge	<i>Esox masquinongy</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	300	0-0.005	48 hours	Peritoneal cavity	Laboratory	None	[32]
Muskellunge	<i>Esox masquinongy</i>	Actinopterygii	PIT tag	300	0-0.011	48 hours	Dorsal musculature	Laboratory	None	[32]
Steelhead trout	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Actinopterygii	Acoustic tags	80	0.2	143 days	Peritoneal cavity	Laboratory	None	[33]
Lake trout	<i>Salvelinus namaycush</i>	Actinopterygii	Anchor tag	660	0.06-0.5	19 years	Dorsal musculature	Wild	Double tag	[34]
Hellbenders	<i>Cryptobranchius alleganiensis</i>	Amphibia	PIT tag	78	0	2 years	Tail musculature	Wild	Genotype	[35]
Common guillemots	<i>Uria aalge</i>	Aves	Metal ring	5594	0.24	20 years	Tarsus	Wild	None	[36]
Greater snow goose	<i>Chen caerulescens atlantica</i>	Aves	Neck collar	7799	0.05	12 years	Neck	Wild	Metal ring	[37]
Lesser snow goose	<i>Chen caerulescens caerulescens</i>	Aves	Neck collar	3078	0.45-0.65	6 years	Neck	Wild	Metal ring	[38]
Red kites	<i>Milvus milvus</i>	Aves	Radiotransmitter	142	0.11	11 years	Backpack harness	Wild	Plastic wing tag	[39]
Abalone	<i>Haliotis kamitschatkana</i>	Gastropoda	PIT tag	62	0.1-0.9	6-15 days	Shell./foot muscle	Laboratory	None	[40]
Grasshoppers	<i>Prionotropis hystrix rhodanica</i>	Insecta	Radio-tracking	442	0.06-0.09	36 days	Pronotum (Glued)	Wild	None	[41]
New Zealand fur seal	<i>Arctocephalus forsteri</i>	Mammalia	Plastic tags	1255	0-0.6	3 years	Fore flipper	Wild	Double tag	[42]
Elephant seal	<i>Mirounga leonina</i>	Mammalia	Plastic tags	8567	0.2	7 years	Hind flipper	Wild	Hot-iron branding	[43]
Elephant seals	<i>Mirounga leonina</i>	Mammalia	Plastic tags	14000	0-0.4	17 years	Hind flipper	Wild	Hot-iron branding	[44]
Grey seals	<i>Halichoerus grypus</i>	Mammalia	Plastic tags	725	0.04-0.27	28 years	Flipper	Wild	Double tag/brand	[45]
Black bears	<i>Ursus americanus</i>	Mammalia	Plastic tags	298	0.094	12 years	Ear	Wild	Double tag/tattoo	[46]
Elephant seal	<i>Mirounga leonina</i>	Mammalia	Plastic tags	8568	0-0.364	8 years	Hind flipper	Wild	Double tag/brand	[47]
Silvery marmoset	<i>Callithrix argentata</i>	Mammalia	PIT tag	4	0.75	8 months	?	Zoo	None	[48]
White-handed gibbon	<i>Hylobates lar</i>	Mammalia	PIT tag	2	0	10 months	?	Zoo	None	[48]
Naked mole rat	<i>Heterocephalus glaber</i>	Mammalia	PIT tag	2	0	8 months	?	Zoo	None	[48]
Himalayan tahr	<i>Hemitragus jemlahicus</i>	Mammalia	PIT tag	9	0	10 months	?	Zoo	None	[48]
Corn snake	<i>Elaphe guttata</i>	Reptilia	PIT tag	15	0.53	9 weeks	neck region	Laboratory	None	[49]

Table 2 – Non exhaustive list of tag loss rate from bibliography. Only studies using CMR methods or studies in control conditions (Laboratory and Zoo) are reported. The mark type, the sample size of the individuals marked, the duration of the study and the location of the mark were reported. If a method is used as permanent mark, the type of 'control' mark is indicated.

References

- Conde DA et al. (2019). *Data gaps and opportunities for comparative and conservation biology*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **116**, 9658–9664. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1816367116>.
- Lentini PE, Bird TJ, Griffiths SR, Godinho LN, Wintle BA (2015). *A global synthesis of survival estimates for microbats*. *Biology Letters* **11**. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2015.0371>.

Sources in Table S1 & S2:

- [1] Gaillard, J., and N. Yoccoz. (2003). Temporal variation in survival of mammals: A case of environmental canalization? *Ecology* 84:3294–3306. <https://doi.org/10.1890/02-0409>
- [2] Sendor, T., & M. Simon. (2003). Population dynamics of the pipistrelle bat: effects of sex, age and winter weather on seasonal survival. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 72:308–320. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2656.2003.00702.x>
- [3] Giavi, S., M. Moretti, F. Bontadina, N. Zambelli, & M. Schaub. (2014). Seasonal Survival Probabilities Suggest Low Migration Mortality in Migrating Bats. *Plos One* 9:e85628. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0085628>
- [4] Smout, S., R. King, & P. Pomeroy. 2011. Integrating heterogeneity of detection and mark loss to estimate survival and transience in UK grey seal colonies. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 48:364–372. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2010.01913.x>
- [5] Benson, J. F., S. J. Jorgensen, J. B. O'Sullivan, C. Winkler, C. F. White, E. Garcia-Rodriguez, O. Sosa-Nishizaki, & C. G. Lowe. (2018). Juvenile survival, competing risks, and spatial variation in mortality risk of a marine apex predator. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 55:2888–2897. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13158>
- [6] Neat, F., Pinto, C., Burrett, I., Cowie, L., Travis, J., Thorburn, J., ... Wright, P. J. (2015). Site fidelity, survival and conservation options for the threatened flapper skate (*Dipturus cf. intermedia*). *Aquatic Conservation-Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 25(1), 6–20. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2472>
- [7] Bradshaw, C. J. A., H. F. Mollet, & M. G. Meekan. (2007). Inferring population trends for the world's largest fish from mark-recapture estimates of survival. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 76:480–489. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2006.01201.x>
- [8] Rudershausen, P. J., J. E. Hightower, J. A. Buckel, M. J. O'Donnell, T. Dubreuil, & B. H. Letcher. (2019). Survival and Density of a Dominant Fish Species Across a Gradient of Urbanization in North Carolina Tidal Creeks. *Estuaries and Coasts* 42:1632–1653. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-019-00575-5>
- [9] Melnychuk, M. C., K. J. Dunton, A. Jordaan, K. A. McKown, & M. G. Frisk. (2017). Informing conservation strategies for the endangered Atlantic sturgeon using acoustic telemetry and multi-state mark-recapture models. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 54:914–925. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12799>
- [10] Hoyle, S. D., Pople, A. R., & Toop, G. J. (2001). Mark-recapture may reveal more about ecology than about population trends: Demography of a threatened ghost bat (*Macroderma gigas*) population. *Austral Ecology*, 26(1), 80–92. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1442-9993.2001.01092.pp.x>
- [11] Amengual, B., Bourhy, H., Lopez-Roig, M., & Serra-Cobo, J. (2007). Temporal Dynamics of European Bat Lyssavirus Type 1 and Survival of *Myotis myotis* Bats in Natural Colonies. *Plos One*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0000566>
- [12] Baker, G. B., Lumsden, L. F., Dettmann, E. B., Schedvin, N. K., Schulz, M., Watkins, D., & Jansen, L. (2001). The effect of forearm bands on insectivorous bats (*Microchiroptera*) in Australia. *Wildlife Research*, 28(3), 229–237. <https://doi.org/10.1071/wr99068>
- [13] Beer, J. R. (1955). Survival and Movements of Banded Big Brown Bats. *Journal of Mammalogy*, 36(2), 242–248. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1375883>

- [14] Boyles, J. G., Walters, B. L., Whitaker, J. O., & Cope, J. B. (2007). A reanalysis of apparent survival rates of Indiana myotis (*Myotis sodalis*). *Acta Chiropterologica*, 9(1), 127–132. [https://doi.org/10.3161/1733-5329\(2007\)9\[127:AROASR\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.3161/1733-5329(2007)9[127:AROASR]2.0.CO;2)
- [15] Ellison, L. E. (2010). A Retrospective Survival Analysis of Townsend's Big-Eared Bat (*Corynorhinus townsendii*) from Washington State. *Northwestern Naturalist*, 91(2), 172–182. <https://doi.org/10.1898/NWN09-10.1>
- [16] Ellison, L. E., O'Shea, T. J., Neubaum, D. J., Neubaum, M. A., Pearce, R. D., & Bowen, R. A. (2007). A comparison of conventional capture versus PIT reader techniques for estimating survival and capture probabilities of big brown bats (*Eptesicus fuscus*). *Acta Chiropterologica*, 9(1), 149–160. [https://doi.org/10.3161/1733-5329\(2007\)9\[149:ACOCCV\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.3161/1733-5329(2007)9[149:ACOCCV]2.0.CO;2)
- [17] Frick, W. F., Rainey, W. E., & Pierson, E. D. (2007). Potential Effects of Environmental Contamination on Yuma Myotis Demography and Population Growth. *Ecological Applications*, 17(4), 1213–1222. <https://doi.org/10.1890/06-1021>
- [18] Gerell, R., & Lundberg, K. (1990). Sexual Differences in Survival Rates of Adult Pipistrelle Bats (*Pipistrellus pipistrellus*) in South Sweden. *Oecologia*, 83(3), 401–404. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00317567>
- [19] Hitchcock, H. B., Keen, R., & Kurta, A. (1984). Survival Rates of *Myotis leibii* and *Eptesicus fuscus* in Southeastern Ontario. *Journal of Mammalogy*, 65(1), 126–130. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1381210>
- [20] Humphrey, S. R., & Cope, J. B. (1976). Population ecology of the little brown bat, *Myotis lucifugus*, in Indiana and north-central Kentucky. *American Society of Mammalogists*. <http://archive.org/details/populationecolog00hump>
- [21] O'Donnell, C. F. J. (2002). Timing of breeding, productivity and survival of long-tailed bats *Chalinolobus tuberculatus* (Chiroptera: Vespertilionidae) in cold-temperate rainforest in New Zealand. *Journal of Zoology*, 257(3), 311–323. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0952836902000912>
- [22] Papadatou, E., Butlin, R. K., Pradel, R., & Altringham, J. D. (2009). Sex-specific roost movements and population dynamics of the vulnerable long-fingered bat, *Myotis capaccinii*. *Biological Conservation*, 142(2), 280–289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2008.10.023>
- [23] Papadatou, Elena, Pradel, R., Schaub, M., Dolch, D., Geiger, H., Ibanez, C., Kerth, G., Popa-Lisseanu, A., Schorcht, W., Teubner, J., & Gimenez, O. (2012). Comparing survival among species with imperfect detection using multilevel analysis of mark-recapture data: A case study on bats. *Ecography*, 35(2), 153–161. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2011.07084.x>
- [24] Papadatou, Eleni, Ibáñez, C., Pradel, R., Juste, J., & Gimenez, O. (2011). Assessing survival in a multi-population system: A case study on bat populations. *Oecologia*, 165(4), 925–933. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-010-1771-5>
- [25] Pryde, M. A., O'Donnell, C. F. J., & Barker, R. J. (2005). Factors influencing survival and long-term population viability of New Zealand long-tailed bats (*Chalinolobus tuberculatus*): Implications for conservation. *Biological Conservation*, 126(2), 175–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.05.006>
- [26] Pryde, Moira A., Lettink, M., & O'Donnell, C. F. J. (2006). Survivorship in two populations of long-tailed bats (*Chalinolobus tuberculatus*) in New Zealand. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology*, 33(2), 85–95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03014223.2006.9518433>
- [27] Rivers, N. M., Butlin, R. K., & Altringham, J. D. (2006). Autumn swarming behaviour of Natterer's bats in the UK: Population size, catchment area and dispersal. *Biological Conservation*, 127(2), 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.08.010>
- [28] Schaub, M., Gimenez, O., Sierro, A., & Arlettaz, R. (2007). Use of integrated modeling to enhance estimates of population dynamics obtained from limited data. *Conservation Biology*, 21(4), 945–955. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2007.00743.x>
- [29] Schorcht, W., Bontadina, F., & Schaub, M. (2009). Variation of adult survival drives population dynamics in a migrating forest bat. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 78(6), 1182–1190. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2009.01577.x>
- [30] Acolas, M. L., Roussel, J. M., Lebel, J. M., and Bagliniere, J. L. (2007). Laboratory experiment on survival, growth and tag retention following PIT injection into the body cavity of juvenile

brown trout (*Salmo trutta*). *Fisheries Research*, 86(2–3), 280–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2007.05.011>

[31] Kaemingk, M. A., Weber, M. J., McKenna, P. R., and Brown, M. L. (2011). Effect of Passive Integrated Transponder Tag Implantation Site on Tag Retention, Growth, and Survival of Two Sizes of Juvenile Bluegills and Yellow Perch. *North American Journal of Fisheries Management*, 31(4), 726–732. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02755947.2011.611863>

[32] Wagner, C. P., Jennings, M. J., Kampa, J. M., and Wahl, D. H. (2007). Survival, growth, and tag retention in age-0 Muskellunge implanted with passive integrated transponders. *North American Journal of Fisheries Management*, 27(3), 873–877. <https://doi.org/10.1577/M06-196.1>

[33] Sandstrom, P. T., Ammann, A. J., Michel, C., Singer, G., Chapman, E. D., Lindley, S., ... Klimley, A. P. (2013). Growth, survival, and tag retention of steelhead trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) and its application to survival estimates. *Environmental Biology of Fishes*, 96(2–3), 145–164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10641-012-0051-0>

[34] Fabrizio, M. C., Nichols, J. D., Hines, J., Swanson, B. L., and Schram, S. T. (1999). Modeling data from double-tagging experiments to estimate heterogeneous rates of tag shedding in lake trout (*Salvelinus namaycush*). <https://doi.org/10.1139/F99-069>

[35] Unger, S. D., Burgmeier, N. G., and Williams, R. N. (2012). Genetic markers reveal high PIT tag retention rates in giant salamanders (*Cryptobranchus alleganiensis*). *Amphibia-Reptilia*, 33(2), 313–317. <https://doi.org/10.1163/156853812X641712>

[36] Reynolds, T. J., King, R., Harwood, J., Frederiksen, M., Harris, M. P., and Wanless, S. (2009). Integrated data analysis in the presence of emigration and mark loss. *Journal of Agricultural, Biological, and Environmental Statistics*, 14(4), 411–431. <https://doi.org/10.1198/jabes.2009.080089>

[37] Juillet, C., Choquet, R., Gauthier, G., and Pradel, R. (2011). A Capture–Recapture model with double-marking, live and dead encounters, and heterogeneity of reporting due to auxiliary mark loss. *Journal of Agricultural, Biological, and Environmental Statistics*, 16(1), 88–104. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13253-010-0035-5>

[38] Conn, P. B., Kendall, W. L., and Samuel, M. D. (2004). A General Model for the Analysis of Mark-Resight, Mark-Recapture, and Band-Recovery Data under Tag Loss. *Biometrics*, 60(4), 900–909. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0006-341X.2004.00245.x>

[39] Tavecchia, G., Adrover, J., Navarro, A. M., and Pradel, R. (2012). Modelling mortality causes in longitudinal data in the presence of tag loss: application to raptor poisoning and electrocution. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 49(1), 297–305. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2011.02074.x>

[40] Hale, J. R., Bouma, J. V., Vadopalas, B., and Friedman, C. S. (2012). Evaluation of Passive Integrated Transponders for Abalone: Tag Placement, Retention, and Effect on Survival. *Journal of Shellfish Research*, 31(3), 789–794. <https://doi.org/10.2983/035.031.0324>

[41] Besnard, A., Piry, S., Berthier, K., Lebreton, J.-D., and Streiff, R. (2007). Modeling survival and mark loss in molting animals: Recapture, dead recoveries, and exuvia recoveries. *Ecology*, 88(2), 289–295. <https://doi.org/10.1890/05-0811>

[42] Bradshaw, C. J. A., Bark6er, R. J., and Davis, L. S. (2000). Modeling tag loss in New Zealand fur seal pups. *Journal of Agricultural Biological and Environmental Statistics*, 5(4), 475–485. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1400661>

[43] Malcolm-White, E., McMahon, C. R., and Cowen, L. L. E. (2020). Complete tag loss in capture–recapture studies affects abundance estimates: An elephant seal case study. *Ecology and Evolution*, 10(5), 2377–2384. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.6052>

[44] Schwarz, L. K., Hindell, M. A., McMahon, C. R., and Costa, D. P. (2012). The implications of assuming independent tag loss in southern elephant seals. *Ecosphere*, 3(9), art81. <https://doi.org/10.1890/ES12-00132.1>

[45] Smout, S., King, R., and Pomeroy, P. (2011). Integrating heterogeneity of detection and mark loss to estimate survival and transience in UK grey seal colonies. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 48(2), 364–372. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2010.01913.x>

- [46] Laake, J. L., Johnson, D. S., Diefenbach, D. R., and Terner, M. A. (2014). Hidden Markov Model for Dependent Mark Loss and Survival Estimation. *Journal of Agricultural Biological and Environmental Statistics*, 19(4), 524–540. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13253-014-0190-1>
- [47] McMahon, C. R., and White, G. C. (2009). Tag loss probabilities are not independent: Assessing and quantifying the assumption of independent tag transition probabilities from direct observations. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 372(1–2), 36–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2009.02.006>
- [48] Elbin, S., and Burger, J. (1994). Implantable Microchips for Individual Identification in Wild and Captive Populations. *Wildlife Society Bulletin*, 22(4), 677–683.
- [49] Roark, A. W., and Dorcas, M. E. (2000). Regional Body Temperature Variation in Corn Snakes Measured Using Temperature-Sensitive Passive Integrated Transponders. *Journal of Herpetology*, 34(3), 481–485. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1565378>